

Computation of Inverse Sum Indeg Uphill Index and Its Polynomial of Certain Graphs

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 21 June 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: V.R. Kulli</p>	<p>In this paper, we introduce the inverse sum indeg uphill index and the inverse sum indeg uphill polynomial of a graph. Also we compute the inverse sum indeg uphill index and its corresponding polynomial of some standard graphs, wheel graphs, gear graphs and helm graphs.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: inverse sum indeg uphill index, inverse sum indeg uphill polynomial, graph.</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

We consider simple graphs which are finite, undirected, connected graphs without loops and multiple edges. Let G be such a graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. The degree $d_G(u)$ of a vertex u is the number of vertices adjacent to u . For undefined notations and technology, we refer [1].

A topological index is a numerical parameter mathematically derived from the graph structure. Several topological indices have been considered in Theoretical Chemistry and many topological indices were defined by using vertex degree concept. The Zagreb, Nirmala, Sombor, Gourava, temperature indices are the most degree based topological indices in Chemical Graph Theory, see [2-28]. Topological indices have their applications in various disciplines in Science and Technology.

A u - v path P in G is a sequence of vertices in G , starting with u and ending at v , such that consecutive vertices in P are adjacent, and no vertex is repeated. A path $\pi = v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{k+1}$ in G is a downhill path if for every $i, 1 \leq i \leq k, d_G(v_i) \geq d_G(v_{i+1})$.

A vertex v is downhill dominates a vertex u if there exists a downhill path originated from u to v . The downhill neighborhood of a vertex v is denoted by $N_{dn}(v)$ and defined as: $N_{dn}(v) = \{u: v \text{ downhill dominates } u\}$. The downhill degree $d_{dn}(v)$ of a vertex v is the number of downhill neighbors of v [29]. Recently, some downhill indices were studied in [30-32].

The uphill domination is introduced by Deering in [33].

A u - v path P in G is a sequence of vertices in G , starting with u and ending at v , such that consecutive vertices in P are adjacent, and no vertex is repeated. A path $\pi = v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{k+1}$ in G is an uphill path if for every $i, 1 \leq i \leq k, d_G(v_i) \leq d_G(v_{i+1})$.

A vertex v uphill dominates a vertex u if there exists an uphill path originated from u to v . The uphill neighborhood of a vertex v is denoted by $N_{up}(v)$ and defined as: $N_{up}(v) = \{u: v \text{ uphill dominates } u\}$. The uphill degree $d_{up}(v)$ of a vertex v is the number of uphill neighbors of v , see [34].

In [35], Vukićević et al. observed that many graph indices are defined simply as the sum of individual bound contributions. They have proposed a class of discrete Adriatic indices to study whether there other possibly significant graph indices of this form. One of these discrete Adriatic indices is the inverse sum indeg index, and this index is defined as

$$ISI(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{d_G(u)d_G(v)}{d_G(u) + d_G(v)}$$

Some inverse sum indices were studied in [36, 37].

Motivated by the inverse sum indeg index, we introduce the inverse sum indeg uphill index of a graph as follows:

The inverse sum indeg uphill index of a graph G is defined as

$$ISIU(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{d_{up}(u)d_{up}(v)}{d_{up}(u) + d_{up}(v)}.$$

In view of the inverse sum indeg uphill index, we propose the inverse sum indeg uphill polynomial of a graph G and it is defined as

$$ISIU(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{d_{up}(u)d_{up}(v)}{d_{up}(u) + d_{up}(v)}}.$$

Recently, some uphill indices were studied such as the Nirmala uphill indices [38], Sombor uphill indices [39] and F-uphill index [40].

In this paper, we compute the inverse sum indeg uphill index and its corresponding polynomial of some standard graphs, wheel graphs, gear graphs and helm graphs.

II. RESULTS FOR SOME STANDARD GRAPHS

Proposition 1. Let G be r -regular with n vertices and $r \geq 2$. Then

$$ISIU(G) = \frac{nr(n-1)}{4}.$$

Proof: Let G be an r -regular graph with n vertices and $r \geq 2$ and $\frac{nr}{2}$ edges. Then $d_{up}(v) = n-1$ for every v in G . We obtain

$$\begin{aligned} ISIU(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{d_{up}(u)d_{up}(v)}{d_{up}(u) + d_{up}(v)} \\ &= \frac{nr}{2} \frac{(n-1)(n-1)}{(n-1) + (n-1)} = \frac{nr(n-1)}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 1.1. Let C_n be a cycle with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$ISIU(C_n) = \frac{n(n-1)}{2}.$$

Corollary 1.2. Let K_n be a complete graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$ISIU(K_n) = \frac{n(n-1)^2}{4}.$$

Proposition 2. Let G be r -regular with n vertices and $r \geq 2$. Then

$$ISIU(G, x) = \frac{nr}{2} x^{\frac{(n-1)}{2}}.$$

Proof: Let G be an r -regular graph with n vertices and $r \geq 2$ and $\frac{nr}{2}$ edges. Then $d_{up}(v) = n-1$ for every v in G . We obtain

$$ISIU(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{d_{up}(u)d_{up}(v)}{d_{up}(u) + d_{up}(v)}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{nr}{2} x^{\frac{(n-1)(n-1)}{(n-1) + (n-1)}} \\ &= \frac{nr}{2} x^{\frac{(n-1)}{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 1.1. Let C_n be a cycle with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$ISIU(C_n, x) = nx^{\frac{(n-1)}{2}}.$$

Corollary 1.2. Let K_n be a complete graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$ISIU(K_n, x) = \frac{n(n-1)}{2} x^{\frac{(n-1)}{2}}.$$

Proposition 3. Let P_n be a path with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$ISIU(P_n) = \frac{2(n^2 - 5n + 6)}{2n - 5} + \frac{(n-3)^2}{2}.$$

Proof: Let P_n be a path with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Clearly, $P=P_n$ has two types of edges based on the downhill degree of end vertices of each edge as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(P) \mid d_{up}(u) = n-2, d_{up}(v) = n-3\}, |E_1| = 2.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(P) \mid d_{up}(u) = d_{up}(v) = n-3\}, |E_2| = n-3.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} ISIU(P) &= \sum_{uv \in E(P)} \frac{d_{up}(u)d_{up}(v)}{d_{up}(u) + d_{up}(v)} \\ &= 2 \frac{(n-2)(n-3)}{(n-2) + (n-3)} + (n-3) \frac{(n-3)(n-3)}{(n-3) + (n-3)} \\ &= \frac{2(n^2 - 5n + 6)}{2n - 5} + \frac{(n-3)^2}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 4. Let P_n be a path with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$ISIU(P_n, x) = 2x^{\frac{(n^2 - 5n + 6)}{2n - 5}} + (n-3)x^{\frac{(n-3)}{2}}.$$

Proof: Let P_n be a path with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Clearly, $P=P_n$ has two types of edges based on the downhill degree of end vertices of each edge as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(P) \mid d_{up}(u) = n-2, d_{up}(v) = n-3\}, |E_1| = 2.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(P) \mid d_{up}(u) = d_{up}(v) = n-3\}, |E_2| = n-3.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} ISIU(P_n, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(P_n)} x^{\frac{d_{up}(u)d_{up}(v)}{d_{up}(u) + d_{up}(v)}} \\ &= 2x^{\frac{(n-2)(n-3)}{(n-2) + (n-3)}} + (n-3)x^{\frac{(n-3)(n-3)}{(n-3) + (n-3)}} \end{aligned}$$

$$= 2x^{\frac{(n^2-5n+6)}{2n-5}} + (n-3)x^{\frac{(n-3)}{2}} = nx^0 + nx^{\frac{n}{2}}$$

III. RESULTS FOR WHEEL GRAPHS

The wheel W_n is the join of C_n and K_1 . Clearly W_n has $n+1$ vertices and $2n$ edges. The vertex K_1 is called apex and the vertices of C_n are called rim vertices.

Figure 1. Wheel W_n

Let W_n be a wheel with $n+1$ vertices and $2n$ edges, $n \geq 4$. Then there are two types of edges based on the downhill degree of end vertices of each edge as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(W_n) \mid d_{up}(u) = 0, d_{up}(v) = n\}, \quad |E_1| = n$$

$$|E_1| = n.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(W_n) \mid d_{up}(u) = d_{up}(v) = n\}, \quad |E_2| = n.$$

$$|E_2| = n.$$

Theorem 1. Let W_n be a wheel with $n+1$ vertices and $2n$ edges, $n \geq 4$. Then

$$ISIU(W_n) = \frac{n^2}{2}.$$

Proof. We deduce

$$ISIU(W_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(W_n)} \frac{d_{up}(u)d_{up}(v)}{d_{up}(u) + d_{up}(v)}$$

$$= \frac{nn' \cdot 0}{0 + n} + \frac{nnn}{n + n}$$

$$= \frac{n^2}{2}.$$

Theorem 2. Let W_n be a wheel with $n+1$ vertices and $2n$ edges, $n \geq 4$. Then

$$ISIU(W_n, x) = nx^0 + nx^{\frac{n}{2}}$$

Proof. We obtain

$$ISIU(W_n, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(W_n)} x^{\frac{d_{up}(u)d_{up}(v)}{d_{up}(u)+d_{up}(v)}}$$

$$= nx^{\frac{0}{n}} + nx^{\frac{n}{n}}$$

IV. RESULTS FOR GEAR GRAPHS

A bipartite wheel graph is a graph obtained from W_n with $n+1$ vertices adding a vertex between each pair of adjacent rim vertices and this graph is denoted by G_n and also called as a gear graph. Clearly, $|V(G_n)| = 2n+1$ and $|E(G_n)| = 3n$. A gear graph G_n is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Gear graph G_n

Let G_n be a gear graph with $2n+1$ vertices, $3n$ edges, $n \geq 4$. Then G_n has two types of edges based on the downhill degree of the vertices of each edge as follows:

$$E_1 = \{u \in E(G_n) \mid d_{up}(u) = 1, d_{up}(v) = 0\}, \quad |E_1| = n.$$

$$E_2 = \{u \in E(G_n) \mid d_{up}(u) = 1, d_{up}(v) = 3\}, \quad |E_2| = 2n.$$

Theorem 3. Let G_n be a gear graph with $2n+1$ vertices, $3n$ edges, $n \geq 4$. Then the inverse sum indeg downhill index of G_n is

$$ISIU(G_n) = \frac{3n}{2}.$$

Proof: We deduce

$$ISIU(G_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(G_n)} \frac{d_{up}(u)d_{up}(v)}{d_{up}(u) + d_{up}(v)}$$

$$= n \left(\frac{1 \times 0}{1 + 0} \right) + 2n \left(\frac{1 \times 3}{1 + 3} \right)$$

$$= \frac{3n}{2}.$$

Theorem 4. Let G_n be a gear graph with $2n+1$ vertices, $3n$ edges, $n \geq 4$. Then the inverse sum indeg downhill polynomial of G_n is

$$ISIDW(G_n, x) = nx^{\frac{2n}{n+1}} + 2nx^0.$$

Proof: We deduce

$$ISIU(G_n, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G_n)} x^{\frac{d_{up}(u)d_{up}(v)}{d_{up}(u)+d_{up}(v)}}$$

$$= nx^{\frac{1 \times 0}{1+0}} + 2nx^{\frac{1 \times 3}{1+3}}$$

$$= nx^0 + 2nx^{\frac{3}{4}}$$

V. RESULTS FOR HELM GRAPHS

The helm graph H_n is a graph obtained from W_n (with $n+1$ vertices) by attaching an end edge to each rim vertex of W_n . Clearly, $|V(H_n)| = 2n+1$ and $|E(H_n)| = 3n$. A graph H_n is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Helm graph H_n

Let H_n be a helm graph with $3n$ edges, $n \geq 5$. Then H_n has three types of edges based on the downhill degree of the vertices of each edge as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(H_n) \mid d_{up}(u) = n+1, d_{up}(v) = n\}, \quad |E_1| = n.$$

$$|E_1| = n.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(H_n) \mid d_{up}(u) = d_{up}(v) = n\}, \quad |E_2| = n.$$

$$|E_2| = n.$$

$$E_3 = \{uv \in E(H_n) \mid d_{up}(u) = n, d_{up}(v) = 0\}, \quad |E_3| = n.$$

$$|E_3| = n.$$

Theorem 5. Let H_n be a helm graph with $2n+1$ vertices, $n \geq 5$. Then the inverse sum indeg downhill index of H_n is

$$ISIU(H_n) = \frac{n^2(n+1)}{2n+1} + \frac{n^2}{2}.$$

Proof: We obtain

$$ISIU(H_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(H_n)} \frac{d_{up}(u)d_{up}(v)}{d_{up}(u) + d_{up}(v)}$$

$$= \frac{n \times (n+1) \times n}{(n+1) + n} + \frac{n \times n \times n}{n + n} + \frac{n \times n \times 0}{n + 0}$$

$$= \frac{n^2(n+1)}{2n+1} + \frac{n^2}{2}.$$

Theorem 6. Let H_n be a helm graph with $2n+1$ vertices, $3n$ edges, $n \geq 5$. Then the inverse sum indeg downhill polynomial of H_n is

$$ISIU(H_n, x) = nx^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2n+1}} + nx^{\frac{n}{2}} + nx^0.$$

Proof: We deduce

$$ISIU(H_n, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(H_n)} x^{\frac{d_{up}(u)d_{up}(v)}{d_{up}(u) + d_{up}(v)}}$$

$$= nx^{\frac{(n+1) \times n}{(n+1) + n}} + nx^{\frac{n \times n}{n + n}} + nx^{\frac{n \times 0}{n + 0}}$$

$$= nx^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2n+1}} + nx^{\frac{n}{2}} + nx^0.$$

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the inverse sum indeg uphill index and its corresponding polynomial of some standard graphs, wheel graphs, gear graphs, helm graphs are determined.

REFERENCES

1. V.R.Kulli, *College Graph Theory*, Vishwa International Publications, Gulbarga, India (2012).
2. I.Gutman and N.Trinajstic, Graph theory and molecular orbitals. Total π -electron energy of alternant hydrocarbons, *Chem. Phys. Let.* 17 (1972) 535-538.
3. A.H.Karim, N.E.Arif and A.M.Ramadan, The M-Polynomial and Nirmala index of certain composite graphs, *Tikrit Journal of Pure Science*, 27(3) (2022) 92-101.
4. B.K.Majhi, V.R.Kulli ad I.N.Cangul, Nirmala leap indices of some chemical drugs against COVID-19, *Journal of Discrete Mathematics and its Applications*, 10(1) (2023) 13-21.
5. V.R.Kulli, I.Gutman, B.Furtula and I.Redzepovic, Sombor, Nirmala Dharwad and F-Sombor indices: A Comparative Study, *SSRG International Journal of Applied Chemistry*, 10(2) (2023) 7-10.
6. S.Raghu, V.R.Kulli, K.M.Niranjana and V.M.Goudar, Nirmala indices of certain antiviral drugs, *International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Research*, 11(11) (2023) 3862-3866.
7. N.K.Raut and G.K.Sanap, On Nirmala indices of carbon nanocone C4[2], *IOSR Journal of Mathematics*, 18(4) (2022) 10-15.
8. N.F.Yalcin, Bounds on Nirmala energy of graphs, *Acta Univ. Sapientiae Informatica*, 14(2) (2022) 302-315.
9. V.R.Kulli, HDR Sombor indices and their exponentials, *International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Research*, 10(7) (2022) 2817-2821.
10. V.R.Kulli, E-Banhatti Sombor indices, *International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Research*, 10(12) (2022) 2986-2994.
11. V.R.Kulli, Euler Sombor Banhatti indices, *International Journal of Engineering Sciences & Research Technology*, 13(5) (2024) 12-45.

12. V.R.Kulli, Status elliptic Sombor and modified status elliptic Sombor indices of graphs, *Journal of Mathematics and Informatics*, 27 (2024) 49-54.
13. V.R.Kulli, G.O.Kizilirmak and Z.B.Pendik, Leap elliptic Sombor indices of some chemical drugs, *International Journal of Mathematical Archive*, 16(4) (2025) 1-8.
14. I.Gutman, I.Redzepovic, G.O.Kizilirmak and V.R.Kulli, Euler Sombor index and its congeners, *Open Journal of Mathematical Sciences*, 9 (2025) 141-148. DOI: 10.30538/oms2025.0249.
15. M.Aruvi, J.M.Joseph and E.Ramganes, The second Gourava index of some graph products, *Advances in Mathematics: Scientific Journal*, 9(12) (2020) 10241-10249.
16. I.Gutman and V.R.Kulli, Estimating the Gourava Sombor index, *Ser. A: Appl. Math. Inform. And Mech.* 16(1) (2024) 47-52.
17. V.R.Kulli, On alpha and gamma Gourava indices, *International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Research*, 12(4) (2024) 4139-4144.
18. K.G.Mirajkar and B.Pooja, On Gourava indices of some chemical graphs, *International Journal of Applied Engineering research*, 14(3) (2019) 743-749.
19. R.P.Somani and V.Jethwani, Introducing new exponential Gourava indices for graphs, *International Journal of Mathematics and Statistics Invention*, 11(3) (2023) 1-5.
20. N.Kansal, P.Garg and O.Singh, Temperature based topological indices and QSPR analysis for COVOD-19 drugs, *Polycyclic Aromatic Compounds*, DOI: 10.1080/10406638.2022.2086271.
21. V.R.Kulli, Multiplicative (a, b)-KA temperature indices of certain nanostructures, *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology*, 66(5) (2020) 137-142.
22. V.R.Kulli, Computing some multiplicative temperature indices of certain networks, *Journal of Mathematics and Informatics* 18 (2020) 139-143.
23. V.R.Kulli, Inverse sum temperature index and multiplicative inverse sum temperature index of certain nanotubes, *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*, 12, 01(c) (2021) 40635-40639.
24. V.R.Kulli, The (a, b)-KA temperature indices of tetrameric 1,3-adamantane, *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*, 12, 02(c) (2021) 40929-40933.
25. V.R.Kulli, Temperature Sombor and temperature Nirmala indices, *International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Research*, 10(9) (2022) 2910-2915.
26. V.R.Kulli, Temperature elliptic Sombor and modified temperature elliptic Sombor indices, *International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Research*, 13(3) (2025) 4906-4910.
27. V.R.Kulli, Reduced temperature indices, *International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Research*, 13(4) (2025) 4906-4910.
28. A.E.Nabeel and N.K.Huussin, Temperature and multiplicative temperature indices of nanotubes, *Tikrit Journal of Pure Science*, 25(4) (2020) 109-116.
29. B.Al-Ahmadi, A.Saleh and W.Al-Shammakh, Downhill Zagreb topological indices of graphs, *International Journal of Analysis and Applications*, 19(2) (2021) 205-227.
30. V.R.Kulli, Downhill Sombor modified downhill Sombor indices of graphs, *Annals of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 31(2) (2025) 107-112.
31. V.R.Kulli, Downhill Nirmala alpha Gourava indices of chloroquine, hydroxychloroquine and remdesivir, *International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Research*, 13(5) (2025) 5276-5284.
32. V.R.Kulli, Harmonic downhill indices of graphs, *Journal of Mathematics and Informatics*, 28 (2025) 33-37.
33. J.Deering, Uphill and downhill domination in graphs and related graph parameters, Thesis, East Tennessee State University, (2013).
34. V.R.Kulli, Harmonic uphill index of graphs, *International Journal of Mathematical Archive*; 16(6) (2025) 1-7.
35. D.Vukicevic, M.Gasperov, Bond additive modeling 1, Adriatic indices, *Croat, Chem.Acta*, 83 (2010) 243-260.
36. V.R.Kulli, Direct and inverse sum Banhatti indices, *International Research Journal of Pure Algebra*, 7(9) (2017) 823-827.
37. J.Sedlar, D.Stevanovic and A.Vasilyev, On the inverse sum indeg index, *Discrete Applied Mathematics*, 184 (2015) 202.
38. V.R.Kulli, Nirmala uphill indices of graphs, *International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology*, to appear.
39. V.R.Kulli, Sombor uphill indices of graphs, *International Journal of Mathematics and Statistics Invention*, to appear.
40. V.R.Kulli, F-uphill index of graphs, *International Journal of Mathematics and its Applications*, to appear.